

EMOTIONAL-EXPRESSIVE MEANS IN THE SPEECH OF THE ILLUSTRATION OF ULUGBEK IN THE DRAMA "THE TRAGEDY OF MIRZO ULUGBEK"

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Annotation. This article analyzes the means of emotional and expressiveness in the speech of the character of Ulugbek in Maqsd Shaikhzoda's drama "The Tragedy of Mirzo Ulugbek". Ulugbek's speeches on stage illuminate his spiritual experiences, suffering, devotion to science, and human tragedy. The author reveals the dramatic power and emotional impact through some examples of speeches in the language of Ulugbek.

Keywords: Ulugbek, drama, emotional-expressiveness, speech, suffering, historical image.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются средства эмоциональности и выразительности в речи персонажа Улугбека в драме Максуда Шайхзода «Трагедия Мирзо Улугбека». Речи Улугбека на сцене освещают его духовные переживания, страдания, преданность науке и человеческую трагедию. Автор раскрывает драматическую силу и эмоциональное воздействие на некоторых примерах речей на языке Улугбека.

Ключевые слова: Улугбек, драма, эмоционально-выразительная речь, страдание, исторический образ.

The process of creating an image in a literary text is multifaceted, and especially in dramatic works this process is manifested in harmony with stage means. In a drama, the hero's speech serves not only to develop the plot, but also to reflect his inner experiences, worldview, emotional state and will. In particular, the analysis of dramatic images created on the basis of historical figures requires a unique approach. In this regard, the drama "The Tragedy of Mirzo Ulugbek" by Iqbol Mirzo occupies a special place among Uzbek classical and modern dramaturgy, in which the inner spiritual world, philosophical views and tragic fate of the image of Ulugbek are vividly depicted. One of the most powerful works in Uzbek dramaturgy that embodies the image of a historical figure in a tragic spirit is the drama "The Tragedy of Mirzo Ulugbek" by Maqsd Shaikhzoda. This work deeply depicts the inner world of Ulugbek, his struggle for knowledge and truth, and his suffering under the pressures of family and society. In particular, Ulugbek's speeches on stage vividly reflect the tragedy and pain in his heart.

Ulugbek's speech has several levels of emotional charge. Each of his words, each phrase oscillates between mental pressure, inner anguish, love for divine knowledge and despair. For example, Ulugbek says: "I lived among the stars, but I perished among people." This sentence reveals the deep drama of the character. Ulugbek connected his spiritual life with science and stars, but among society and his loved ones he feels like an outsider, even a victim. The word "stars" here is used as a symbol of exaltation, truth and beauty, while "people" is used as a symbol of baseness, envy and betrayal.

Another powerful emotional speech that reveals Ulugbek's tragic fate: "If I say my child - my murderer, if I say my heart - my enemy. What is this situation?" Through these words, he openly expresses his spiritual oppression by the betrayal of his son Abdullatif. Ulugbek here intensifies his suffering through a rhetorical question. The combination of the images of the child and the enemy in one person intensifies the dramatic conflict. The following speech, expressing loyalty to science, reveals the main inner essence of Ulugbek's image: "Science is the mirror of the soul, and whoever darkens it has lost his soul." Along with the emotional burden, this thought has a deep philosophical depth.

Ulugbek equates knowledge with the soul and considers its loss to be a loss of humanity. In another speech of Ulugbek, a tragic tone is strongly expressed: "I searched for truth in this life, but I was trapped under mountains full of lies." Here, the metaphor of "mountains" expresses the power of social pressure and oppression. It conveys its suffering in a picturesque way, delivering a spiritual shock to the reader or viewer. By imbuing the speech of the character of Ulugbek with such emotional means, Sheikhzoda decorates it not with a simple historical image, but with experiences familiar to modern man.

In conclusion, in the drama "The Tragedy of Mirzo Ulugbek", the speech of the character of Ulugbek forms the spiritual and artistic basis of the work. The emotional-expressive means used in the speeches reveal the complex inner world of Ulugbek through metaphors, rhetorical questions, allegories and epithets. This reveals him as a tragic hero of any time, not just his own. In the drama "The Tragedy of Mirzo Ulugbek", the main character - the character of Ulugbek - is revealed through his speech not only as a symbol of science, justice and spirituality of his time, but also shows the criterion of human tragedies, spiritual suffering and willpower. The emotional-expressive means embedded in the hero's speech by the playwright serve as an important tool in expressing the complex psychological states of the character. The emotional power of speech, internal drama, repetitions, and the expression of mental tension give the image depth, liveliness, and naturalness. Thus, the verbal portrait of Ulugbek enhances the overall ideological and artistic load of the dramatic work and evokes a strong aesthetic impression on the viewer.

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